

Arctic ROADS Process Workbook

[Theme/EP name]

Note: this version of the Arctic ROADS Process Workbook is meant to show what content is requested as part of the documentation package developed through the process. We encourage Expert Panels to use the version in Google Docs, and as such all of the links currently point to the Google Doc version of this document.

Contact information

Facilitators:

ROADS AP Point of Contact:

[Suggested] Two external reviewers for each Phase:

Phase I:

Phase II:

Phase III:

Phase IV:

Instructions:

Phase I - Fill out (1) [Introduction](#), (2) [Process Questions](#) (including whatever detail you have available for the proposed work in Phase II and III: you will not be evaluated on these but AP can provide feedback on your proposed methods), and start describing (4) [information use cases](#).

Phase II - Update (2) [Process Questions](#), respond to AP comments and feedback on Phase I (as needed). Fill out (3) [Societal Benefits](#) and provide more detail on (4) [information use cases](#).

Phase III - update (2) [Process Questions](#) and Phase I/II (if needed). Fill out [\(5\) SAV definition](#), (6) [observing requirements](#), and (7) [information and data system requirements](#).

Phase IV: update (2) [Process Questions](#) and Phase I/II/III (if needed). Fill out (8) [Implementation strategies](#).

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1. Introduction (Phase I)

1. Abstract of the proposed Expert Panel [300 words].

2. Overview of the proposed Expert Panel [1000 words], including:
 - 1) Scope: Include an overview of the topical/focal area, the geographic focus and a short description of alignment with the ROADS' Guiding Principles (more detailed description in [Part 2 Section 0.1](#)).
 - 2) Societal relevance: Please briefly characterize the societal relevance of the proposed EP's thematic focus and any initial ideas for how you plan to evaluate the culturally-relevant societal benefit(s).
 - 3) Purpose: Describe the overall goals of this EP in the context of the ROADS process, including the significant shortcomings of the current Arctic observing and data systems under this theme.
 - 4) Target audience: ROADS develops requirements and strategies for organizations engaged in data collection and sharing. Please describe some of the target audiences for your recommendations, including those that are already engaged on the EP. Describe who else might engage in or provide funding or support for implementing the types of strategies that you are aiming to develop.
 - 5) Grounding vision: Share any vision that you may already have for what success would look like. A vision is an aspirational statement that describes the impact that this EP will have made in a 10-15 year time frame.

2. Process (Update throughout Phases I-IV)

2.a. Membership of the EP

Provide a description of the membership of the EP (including facilitators). For each person who has contributed to the EP, include their name, affiliation, relevant expertise, role on the EP, and what phase(s) of the process they participated in.

Please list any other parties providing input or feedback to the EP, including the nature of their participation

2.b. Applying the Guiding Principles

How does the work of your expert panel reflect guiding principle #1 (Inclusion)?

How does the work of your expert panel reflect guiding principle #2 (equity)?

How does the work of your expert panel reflect guiding principle #3 (support societal benefits)?

How does the work of your expert panel reflect guiding principle #4 (build on what exists)?

How does the work of your expert panel reflect guiding principle #5 (step-by-step progress)?

2.c. Process questions

2.c.1 Phase I process questions:

- 1) How does the EP plan to convene and communicate? [100 words]

- 2) Identify planned mechanisms through which broader input can be included in the work of the EP. Reference any engagement frameworks that will be used. [100 words]
- 3) How will the EP make decisions and record these decisions? What guidelines for participation do you plan to use or develop? [100 words]
- 4) Please provide confirmation that you have met the required ethical review boards, permitting, and approvals for the relevant research institution and partnering community requirements. [100 words]
- 5) Describe any relationship/relevance to other Expert Panels. [100 words]
- 6) Expected phase timeline through the Integrated Advisory Process. [100 words]
- 7) Briefly identify funding needs for the EP members and activities. What is the plan to secure funding to meet these needs? [300 words]
- 8) How is the EP engaging the funders you imagine would be involved in the implementation of the EP recommendations and developing SAVs? [100 words]

2.C.2 Phase II process questions:

1. Summarize the approach (e.g., method, deliberations, engagement, evaluation tools) taken to identify and assess societal benefit and develop use cases in Phase II of the Expert Panel's work [500 words].
 - a. Describe any specific benefit framework(s) used and how it/they informed the assessment.
 - b. Describe specific areas within the frameworks(s) that were prioritized by the Expert Panel.

2.C.3 Phase III process questions:

1. Describe your approach to specifying requirements for each SAV. As your SAVs may span multiple existing specifications found in other variable-based frameworks, it is acceptable to adopt a different approach to requirements for each SAV or Sub-variable under this Expert Panel. [300 words]

2. Describe how the EP's recommendations for observing system requirements described in this document "complement" and improve upon existing observing systems (Guiding Principle 4). [300 words]

3. Describe how the EP's recommendations for data systems requirements described in this document "complement and integrate" existing data systems. For example, which data centers or producers have you conferred with in drafting these recommendations (Guiding Principle 4)? [300 words]

4. Describe your approach to specifying data system requirements for each SAV. As your SAVs may span multiple existing data systems, it is acceptable to adopt a different approach to requirements for each SAV under this Expert Panel. This description will be evaluated based on how the Expert Panel is addressing things like open/accessible data and the requirements needed to respect data sovereignty. [300 words]

3. Societal Benefit Assessment and candidate SAVs (Phase II)

Describe the results of the societal benefit assessment. [This may be several pages, with figures or other diagrams as necessary]

1. What are your main findings from your societal benefit assessment? [500 words]

3.b. For each candidate SAV identified in this phase, answer 2-4 in this section:

2. Describe the candidate SAVs identified for further work under this EP and how did societal benefit analysis support that identification? If a specific benefit area was a focal point, please indicate that. [300 words per candidate SAV]
3. How are aspects of this candidate SAV already supported through other efforts (e.g., Global networks, other EPs, Arctic Council WG's)? How does the EP propose to engage those efforts, if they are not already involved? [500 words per SAV]
4. What are the key opportunities that have been identified in developing this SAV (Example: improved understanding or new public services)? [150 words per SAV]

4. Information use case summaries (Phase II-III)

For each prioritized societal benefit area, provide specific examples of how information related to expert panel theme EP thematic scope is or could be used.

For each information use case, describe the relevant:

- User or Group
- Decision or Action that user would need to take
- Information currently used for this decision or action
- Desired information for use
- What would improve with “Desired” Information (tie to Societal Benefits prioritized earlier in this phase, identifying where scenarios speak to a specific scale or region)

5. SAV definitions (Phase III)

Include the plain language definitions and references to definitions/ontologies for each SAV here, including sub-variables where appropriate. EPs may deviate from the table format if needed.

Shared Arctic Variable	Sub-Variables (optional)	Plain Language Definition	Reference for this definition

6. Observing Requirements (Phase III)

The Phase III section of the ROADS Handbook Part II has instructions for filling out this section of the Workbook.

One approach to organizing observing requirements would be to fill out the following table for each *information use case* and *SAV* described in the previous sections. Not all the rows will be applicable to every scenario. You can organize this information in another way if it makes more sense.

SAV/Information use case: _____

Specification	Necessary to have (minimum acceptable for use)	Nice to have (optimal for use)
Observing mode: in situ, remote sensing, Indigenous Knowledge and/or community observations		
Spatial resolution		
Frequency/time resolution		
Spatial coverage of observations		
Tolerance for uncertainty		
Other requirements		

Please briefly describe the feasibility of observing each of the SAVs in accordance with the requirements identified above.

7. Information and data system requirements (Phase III)

Please detail the

One approach to organizing observing requirements would be to fill out the following table for each information use case described in the previous sections. Not all the rows will be applicable to every scenario. You can organize this information in another way if it makes more sense.

SAV/Use case: _____

Categories of requirements	User's requirements for information access	What data systems are necessary to meet those requirements?	Nice to have
Timely			
Findable			
Accessible			
Interoperable			
Reusable			
Collective benefit			
Authority to control			
Responsibility			
Ethics			

Please briefly describe the feasibility of executing the data and information systems for each of the SAVs in accordance with the requirements identified.

8. Implementation strategy (Phase IV)

Please describe a strategy for implementation that meets some or all of the needs identified in the previous sections. This strategy should outline the key organizations that will support efforts, identify how data will be managed and shared, how data sovereignty - where applicable - will be upheld.

Further details of the Implementation Strategy documentation guidance will be developed following the 2026 AOS.